

THEORY OF DESIGN

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SUMMARY

It was 3rd century BC Rome, when the Roman Republic began to expand its territory and develop its bureaucratic system. During this period, there was a lot of change and construction was rampant. The Romans recognized that large-scale projects required structure. As such, the term **designators** was used to distinguish individuals with the same name or to assign individuals to specific roles or positions during the period of change^[1]. The word design comes from the word designators and has evolved over centuries as most things do - which will be a central discussion in this paper. Based on this origin, it can be shown that Design is the definition, through which nature communicates with us. I invite you to explore this analysis of design with me.

ABSTRACT

At the heart of a concept is its **meaning** and hidden in every design is a concept. Every design is a **token**^[3] or version of an idea, no two tokens are the same. A basic example of this is two balls of the same shape and size but of different colors, the variation in color alone makes them different tokens. Every design also has a teleological basis, this is grounded in its **function** or purpose. The function of a design is the single most important aspect of a design. Furthermore, **Patterns** are to be considered when designing^[4]. Historical patterns, industrial patterns and behavioral patterns will show you the space for the design - there is a time for everything. Every idea has its place on a **spectrum** or continuum and the spectrums are of different kinds related to all of the aforementioned highlighted topics. The **effect** a design is to have is closely associated with the meaning of the concept on which the design is based and the quality of the design is defined by the position of the token on the spectrum and where it appears in terms of the various patterns observed. Like nature, designs **evolve**, the evolution of a design is

continuous. Designs don't die, they **adapt**, the ability of a design to adapt or be adapted to different functions determines its **fitness** - survival of the fittest. However, it is important to note that while evolution in its primitive stages may have been a process of natural selection, it has "evolved" into a process of **optimizing** designs. Science tells us via the concept of **entropy** that irreversible processes in closed systems naturally tend to disorder, this is to be held at the center of the designers' thought process while exploring a design. Patterns of order and chaos are to be carefully examined. Entropy tells us that chaos is the natural state of most things and order emerges from chaos, thus, worthy of observation is the cycle of order and chaos. Lastly, designs are not to be discarded under any circumstance, every design has its place on a spectrum, the law of conservation is applicable here - "designs" can never be created or destroyed.

KEY VARIABLES

Merit (*noun*) - *the quality of being particularly good or worthy, especially so as to deserve praise or reward:* In terms of a design, merit can be defined as a simple ratio of **Functionality** to **Accuracy**. Higher Merit indicates a better design, however it must be considered with optimality of the design.

Functionality (*noun*) - *the quality of being suited to serve a purpose well:* Functionality is the way we make sense of the design, a design with no function has no space in time.

Accuracy (*noun*) - *the quality or state of being correct or precise:* Accuracy is related to the information used in building the design. This may be based on various things - including the sources of the information & the frequency of occurrence of the information. The accuracy variable is of utmost importance when determining the quality of information. Incomplete information is better than inaccurate information.

Novelty (*noun*) - *the quality of being new, original, or unusual*: Novelty can be defined as a simple ratio of **Originality** to **Persistence**. Novelty gives an indication of the uniqueness of a concept and a higher value ultimately means the concept is more unique.

Originality (*noun*) - *the ability to think independently and creatively*: Originality tells us where the concept sits on a spectrum. Higher originality is not always better. For instance where you have to develop a new technology.

Persistence (*noun*) - *the continued or prolonged existence of something*: The persistence variable has to do with the information being utilized in building a design. Information that may be retracted or changed during the lifespan of a design will have an effect on the fitness of the design.

TYPES OF DESIGN

There are various types of designs depending on the effect you are trying to impress on the viewer or user of the design. The different types of designs complement each other when integrated properly during the construction of the design. The five types of designs I have observed are: Natural, Functional, Classical, Native and Aesthetic designs.

1. **Natural designs** are designs based on nature or modeled after nature. Nature is the best designer and should be observed as much as possible when building designs. Some examples include Spider Webs, Underground Fungi networks and Sunlight. Scientists have observed a crystal-like property of spider webs^[2]. By observing nature one may devise a way to model holographic display technology after the spider web based on the crystal nature of the web. Underground Fungi networks are a mechanism that trees use to communicate and exchange nutrients with one another, this can be applied to farming and fertilizer distribution technology. Sunlight has already been harnessed via solar panels to supply power.

Fig. 1 A spider web with a dragon fly in view. Designs based on nature are some of the most optimal (credit: Pixabay)

Fig. 2 A network of mycelium. They are usually found underground and emerge above ground as mushrooms. Learning from their rich network, communication and exchange properties could birth the next generation of agricultural technology. (credit: ResearchGate)

Fig.3 A row of solar panels. The next energy or third industrial revolution is already in full swing. Global warming and rising temperatures forced

us to look to more sustainable and efficient means of harnessing energy (credit: Pexels).

- 2. **Functional designs** are designs based on the function of the thing being designed. These designs are built to fit a specific function. Every design is centered around its function. Some examples include money, road networks and windmills. Money was invented for one purpose - to enable trade^[5] - this is a classic example of a functional design. Road networks, when properly designed, map the quickest route to get from one place to another. Windmills, just like solar panels in the previous type, are for the sole purpose of harnessing high winds to generate power.

Fig. 4 A depiction of Bitcoin and real \$100 bills. Money was one of the greatest inventions, it has been used to give value to goods, services and economies. It also facilitates the exchange of the aforementioned valuables. Like most things the concept of money evolves, crypto - the most recent evolution - has both supporters and opponents but is a fine example of optimizing a design (credit: Pexels).

Fig. 5 The USA's road map (above) and the UAE's road map (below). Both exquisite designs but one more complex than the other. This could be due to factors such as the variance in size of both countries in terms of population and landmass (credit: Pinterest, Nationsonline).

Fig. 6 Windmills - Old Design(above), Modern Design(below). They were a precursor to solar panels in the energy revolution. However, with increased urbanization and the development of cities with tall buildings, windmills could not be standardized as a means of harnessing energy (credit: Pexels).

3. **Classical designs** are designs based on the contemporary standard of designs. Every period in time has specific designs that define them. The most basic and broadest example is the idea of “the Age”. We are currently moving into the intelligence age from the information age. Designs in specific ages are usually centered around broad ideas with a constellation of tokens to build on. Some classical designs include Artificial Intelligence (Intelligence Age), the wooden plow (Agricultural Age) and the cotton gin (Industrial Age). Artificial intelligence is going to define the coming age, however, after that age passes, the design will still persist via evolution. Building on the AI example, the wooden plow was of utmost importance to the early stages of the Agricultural age. The wooden plow later evolved into a metal plow which later led to the development of more optimal designs, like tractors, with which farmers could yield more crops faster. The cotton gin also accelerated the processing of seed cotton, which in turn led to growth of the textile industry.

Fig. 7 A wooden plow. The Agricultural Revolution is the most important revolution in human history and possibly the longest lasting. As such, all impactful technologies that have enhanced the production of food are worthy of discussion and observation (credit: Craiyon).

Fig. 8 A graphic of a cotton gin. Fashion is the offspring of agriculture and the invention of the cotton gin optimized the processing of seed cotton into textiles. Fashion being the offspring of agriculture (Textiles being the offspring of the Seed) is an abstract example of the spectrum discussed earlier. While one person sees ideas in harvesting the seed another person sees ideas in processing the seeds (credit: Wikimedia).

4. **Native designs** are designs specific to a particular place. Native designs are also a factor of time but tend to last long. You hear of old English buildings, Persian rugs and tessellated Islamic designs. Conflict or wars tend to be catalysts in the evolution of native designs. Old English designs were carried from England to New England during the migration from Europe to the Americas. Persian rugs are of high value both in Iran (formerly Persia) and internationally and are or used to be a symbol of opulence. Tessellated Islamic designs were based on the discoveries of the highly intellectual Arabic mathematicians of the 14th century.

Fig. 9 An Old English house. This is an example of the combination of a native and classical design. These designs were native to England from the 5th to the 15th century and are still a major part of the imageability^[6] of English towns (credit: Pixabay).

Fig. 10 Persian rugs are a thing of aesthetic pleasure and were also originally native to Persia. They defined a period of welfare in Persia and helped spread Persian culture around the world as the rugs traveled commercially (credit: Pexels).

Fig. 11 Tessellated designs are pleasurable both to the mathematical and non-mathematical observer alike. They are an example of the application of patterns and also express the importance of Merit and Novelty discussed earlier (credit: Pexels).

- 5. Aesthetic designs** are designs built to deliver a specific aesthetic. Designs based on aesthetics appeal to various senses with the ultimate goal being the well-being of the end user of the design. Some examples include flower vases, picture frames and brick houses. Flower vases in a home are designed to grab the attention of visitors and convey a feeling to all who observe them. Picture frames are also designed to compliment the pictures they hold. Brick houses also convey a specific feeling and are an example of the combination of two types of designs (Aesthetic and Classical).

Fig. 12 A golden flower vase is bound to catch the attention of any observer - not just because of the beautiful tulips it contains (functionality) but also because of the material it is made of and the design of the vase (credit: Craiyon).

Fig. 13 A classic picture frame design holding a black and white wedding picture will convey a

feeling of the pre-color photo period. This serves both functional and aesthetic purposes (credit: DALL-E).

Fig. 14 A row of red brick houses (above) and the interior wall of a house built with bricks. Both images convey a special feeling. The interior of the house is complemented by the furniture and the light fittings used (credit: Pexels).

It is important to note that designs may incorporate more than one type of design and the optimal design will most definitely be the intersection of multiple types of designs. Furniture is usually a combination of Functional and Aesthetic designs. Solar panels are a combination of Natural, Functional and Classical designs. The aforementioned Persian rugs and other local fashions are a combination of Native and Aesthetic designs. Moroccan architecture is an example of a combination of Native and Classical designs. Living walls are an example of Natural and Aesthetic designs. Most designs regardless of the combinations that are chosen have a functional aspect to it, the function of a design should always be at the center of the design.

THE OPTIMAL DESIGN

For every idea there may be multiple concept tokens and the design of every token has its place but it is necessary to search for the optimal design. However, it is important to note that the optimal design of a well-defined concept will always emerge via the processes of evolution and adaptation and will be the "fittest" design.

There are a few reasons why it is important to search for the optimal design:

1. To find out if an optimal design exists: While the concept of a single "optimal" design may be elusive, the pursuit of an optimal design can still drive innovation and improvement in the design process.
2. To create more meaningful designs: Ultimately, the purpose of design is to improve people's lives, and exploring the optimal design can help designers better understand and meet user needs and desires, resulting in more impactful and meaningful designs.
3. To develop new & more optimal designs: Designers are constantly striving to improve and innovate, and exploring the optimal design can provide a framework for exploring new possibilities and creating more optimal designs.
4. To optimize existing designs: As designs are implemented and used, weaknesses and areas for improvement may become apparent. Exploring the optimal design can help identify these issues and guide efforts to optimize and improve the design.
5. To find out if a specific design is the optimal design: While the focus of design should ultimately be on creating meaningful and impactful designs, there is also value in understanding whether a specific design is the most optimal solution for a given problem or context.
6. To make design more accessible: Design can sometimes seem intimidating or inaccessible to non-designers, but a proper exploration of the optimal design can make design concepts and processes more approachable and understandable to a wider audience.
7. To enhance creativity: Creativity is a key aspect of design, and proper exploration of the optimal design can provide inspiration and guidance for pushing boundaries and exploring new possibilities.

8. To improve collaboration: Design is often a collaborative process, and exploring the optimal design can help different designers work together more effectively. Through this Theory, we provide a common language and framework for understanding each other's perspectives.

9. To improve communication among designers and stakeholders: Clear and effective communication is essential for successful design projects, and a theory of design can help ensure that everyone is on the same page and working towards the same goals.

Designs thrive in restrictions. A good method of exploration is considering the question - "what can't we do?", "what are the mental & moral qualities of the design?" and "which qualities fall outside those constraints?" An example is: don't sit on the arms of a chair, that's not the function of the design. Some restrictions can open the designers eyes to cipher functions, which will be discussed later in this document. Some types of constraints to be considered include: **Natural, Cultural, Material, Financial, Time, Legal, Technical and User Constraints**. There are probably more constraints to be considered but these are the few I propose via this document.

A design is based on information and a specific concept. Information is defined as the process of giving form and the form is given by the "message" encrypted in the information. This is why to compute the optimality of a design we consider the amount of information being processed and the quality of information being used to build the design. I used the word "encrypted" earlier to emphasize the importance of the quality variable. To illustrate this: you have two students in a classroom being fed the same information, however, one student scores 90 on the test and another scores 75, this has nothing to do with the actual data but with the form assumed by the student. There are various factors that could affect this including the method of teaching, language used and other things, this is why it is important that the information - for a given subject - is of fine quality. As far as the amount of information, more information is not always better, for certain subjects more information may be required, especially in novel subjects, this is why it is important to understand the core concept properly before you begin calculations

(more on method of calculation to follow). Continuing the thought of concept, the uniqueness of the concept is of utmost importance and affects the way information is gathered and processed. A unique concept is not always required for a design to be optimized (as illustrated by the nine reasons above), it is important to consider the spectrum discussed earlier in this document.

Consider the formula for the optimal design below:

$$D = \left(\int I_q \times I_a dt \right) \div \left(\int C_u dt \right)$$

Where:

- D = the optimality of the design**
- I_q = the quality of information**
- I_a = the amount of information**
- C_u = the uniqueness of the concept**

I_a is calculated by taking the base-2 logarithm of a number that "symbolizes" the amount of information (N) - this might be the number of data sources, the number of references and so on, depending on the specific case - this is done to convert the amount of information to bits, which is the standard unit of information.

$$I_a = \log_2 (N)$$

$$I_q = (P \times R) \div (1 - A)$$

P is the persistence of the information being used, this has to do with the validity of the information. A lot of theories and formulas are developed, accepted and even applied but are later rejected due to various emergences or other less desirable reasons. To calculate P, we compare the change in information between two periods. This comparison tells us how much the information - or the message being conveyed by the information - has changed between those periods. **P** is measured in bits. Consider the formula below:

$$P = I_a(t_2) - I_a(t_1)$$

R is the relevance of the information - or the message being conveyed by the information - this is closely

related to the Persistence (**P**) variable. To calculate the relevance, we consider the current state of the technology (**S_t**), the space available for the technology (**S_p**) and the demand for the technology (**C**). Of these three variables being considered only **S_t** has a formula, **S_p** and **C** are determined via various other techniques including using revenue and market size. **S_t** is determined by dividing the current state (**C_s**) by the ideal state (**I_s**). The current state is a measure of the present state of the technology in subject while the ideal state is the expected best state of the technology (this is based on predictions). **R** has no unit and is scaled to a maximum value of 1.

$$R = (S_t + S_p + C) \div 3$$

$$S_t = C_s \div I_s$$

A is the accuracy of the information being considered and is the most important part of the information function. It is also the most abstract part of the information function as there are no set rules for determining the accuracy. The accuracy can be determined using various techniques including determining the number of references, the performance of the technology and so on. *It is important to note that incomplete information is better than inaccurate information.*

I_q is measured in bits, just like I_a. The information value determined by the information function will then be in bits².

$$C_u = [(C_r \times O)^{0.5} + F] \div 2$$

C_r is the creativity of the concept. Creativity has previously been abstract and immeasurable, however, I propose the formula below:

$$C_r = (1 + S) - 1$$

where **S** is the saturation and is a depiction of the frequency of the occurrence of the concept. It is determined by comparing the frequency (**F_C**) of the concept being evaluated to the frequency (**F_B**) of a base concept.

$$S = \log_{10}(F_C) + \log_{10}(F_B)$$

O is the originality of the concept and similar to creativity but instead of being a factor of frequency it is a factor of time.

$$O = 1 - (t + T)$$

t is the amount of time the concept has been around while **T** (threshold) is the lifespan of the concept or the amount of time before the concept loses relevance.

F is the functionality of the concept and is analogous to the accuracy variable in the information function. It is abstract and does not always have a fixed formula. However, I propose considering five (5) variables in determining the functionality: **Accessibility, Cost Effectiveness, Efficiency, Flexibility and Sustainability**. Not every concept will present clear cut methods to determine these five variables, however successful resolution in determining the functionality of a concept will always yield great reward. Functionality is more important than the accuracy in the larger design schema because as discussed earlier, every design is assigned a task or function, in other words, functionality is the way we make sense of a design and a design with no function has no place in time, so it is important that the determination of the functionality is done carefully.

C_u is measured in engrams

Now that we have considered all the variables needed to determine the optimality of a design (**D**). Let us consider some other ways to assess a design which were introduced in the key variables section - Merit (**M**) & Novelty (**N_o**).

$$M = F \div A$$

$$N_o = O \div P$$

It is important to note that both variables require two other variables - one from the information function and one from the concept function in both instances. It is also worthy of observation, that the variable from the information function is the denominator in both variables.

Higher Merit, indicates a better quality design. Observing the equation, it goes without saying, that higher functionality yields a higher merit. Similarly, lower accuracy yields higher merit - however, it is important to note that higher accuracy is always preferred.

Higher Novelty on the other hand, is not always better. Consider the phrase: "reinventing the wheel". In some design cases, optimizing a design is more important than redesigning it, remember the function is not to change.

Novelty is also important in determining which method to apply to the calculation:

1. Information first: this requires you to calculate the information function first and aids in the prediction of the optimality of the design. This is the best method for a design that has a lower novelty score - or is not the first of its kind.

2. Concept First: this requires you to calculate the concept function first and provides a better understanding of the nature of the concept which may then aid the computation of the information function. This is the best method for a design that has a higher novelty score - or is the first of its kind.

A great design that efficiently serves its function and that is founded on less information is more optimal, contingent on the accuracy of the information. However, there are some questions to consider here: for a given value of D derived using our equation above, what range of values is considered optimal? Will this vary depending on the design?

To conclude this section, I will like to describe the unit of design. **Engrams (n)** are a measure of the amount of thought put into something, it was previously introduced after we presented the uniqueness of the concept function, which is also measured in engrams. The Information function is given in bits² as discussed earlier, so it is necessary to convert it to **engrams**.

$$1 \text{ bits}^2 = 11.0217 \text{ n}^2$$

Dividing the value given by the information function which is in n² by the value given by the concept function which is in n will give us a final Design value in n.

The following question then arises, For a given design, is it more optimal to use more engrams or less engrams in your design. My answer to this question is that it depends on the nature of the design being considered. For more novel designs, intuition proposes that it will require more engrams to attain design optimality. However, for a less novel design, with a wider spectrum of ideas and more concept tokens, it appears that fewer engrams will produce a more optimal design.

The concept of Conservation of Energy reemerges - reconsider the phrase "reinventing the wheel" - to ensure that your design is optimal it is important to conserve energy where necessary. This entails learning from nature (the best designer), history (the greatest pattern) and imagination (the best expression).

IMPACT

The Optimal design is optimal in the sense that it is easily reproducible. This means that the design has a utilitarian quality to it. Utilitarianism is defined as the doctrine that actions are right if they are useful or for the benefit of a majority ([Oxford Languages](#)). So if design is about well-being, then the optimal design is about a "utilitarian" well-being. This means that the optimal design serves more people than it doesn't serve. The optimal design inspires faith in all observers of the design, when you see a properly designed chair - that is in a good state - you have the conviction that when you sit on the chair it will not give way under you. The optimal design, in a sense, is a factor of health. Via a conversation with ChatGPT, I was able to uncover the fundamental function of design as "The Stimulation of Well-Being". Stimulation means to raise levels of physiological or nervous activity in (the body or any biological system) or encourage interest or activity in something. This is the impact the optimal design should have on the observer or user of the design. Impact is of utmost importance when discussing a design because it is a factor of **Merit**. In physics the point of impact (or collision) is defined as the sudden, forceful coming together in direct contact of two bodies ([Britannica](#)). For a design, this is the point of "first impression" and as they say, the first impression lasts longest.

CONCLUSION

Building on the thought introduced in the Abstract section, there is not one optimal design but there is usually an optimal range within which concepts that are close on the spectrum fall into. In the same section, we discussed evolution and if nature has taught us anything it is that evolution will only learn to optimize faster - might this be a reason why time seems to speed up as we get older? (this might be a worthy thought experiment).

If the goal of optimizing a design is to create a Utilitarian Well-Being, then standardization should be at the center of any design journey. The internet is a great example of a design that has been repeatedly optimized and standardized. At the time of this writing, standardization of the internet is still ongoing but is currently limited by things like cost and literacy. With the rapid advancements in technology it will be accessible to all in the near future. Is your design accessible? This brings the concept of wants and needs into focus. Our basic instincts define our needs, and the most fundamental need we have as humans is food." **Accessibility** is an important factor in the discussion of wants and needs. Building on the example of food, the cheaper organic foods get, the more people will include them in their diets - but in the mean time, the people that want organic foods are the people who are both aware of their existence and can afford them. As you can see, this is closely related to standardization. A thought to ponder is: "what is next in the evolution of computers? Taking into consideration Moore's Law" - might it be accessibility? Standardization does three things: 1. It propagates the effect of the design - "well-being", 2. It assists nature via evolution in her optimization mandate and 3. It will make the designer wealthy.

Every design has a core function but also has random or cipher functions that don't fall within the core functions. Examining, understanding and accommodating both core and cipher functions during the design journey has several benefits including diverse product offerings that can lead to higher revenues. cipher functions or "Hacks" have existed since the invention of the first technology (which we will discuss shortly). These hacks led to the development of new technologies and applications. With this, I introduce another important variable that needs to be examined during the design journey:

Expectation (E). Expectation is a factor of probability, the best way to explore this variable is to ask: "How will the user expect this design to work?" or "What is the probability that a user will use this design for a specific application?", there are many other ways the questions can be phrased but these can be applied to any design. Expectation (always expressed in engrams) has a standard formula^[7].

There are two unique cases to be consider:

1. Where the core and cipher functions are dependent on each other. The **Expectation** (E_{core} or E_{cipher}) of either of the functions being applied to the design by the user is given by the product of the probability (P_{core} or P_{cipher}) of that function being applied and the sum of all functionality (F).

2. Where the core and cipher functions are independent of each other. The **Expectation** (E) is given by the product of the probabilities of each function and the sum of all functionality (F):

$$E = F \times P_{\text{core}} \times P_{\text{cipher}}$$

Design is a form of constant communication and communication is the exchange of information. The process of design is a constant exchange between the Objective Designer and the Subjective User or Observer and doesn't end when the design has been delivered but is a continuous cycle, consider nature's "Circle of Life". A design should be formed in such a way that it suggests its application to the user - when you see a chair, no one has to tell you its purpose instead the chair reaches out to you and tells you "sit on me" and a good chair design might add the word "please" to that communication. Another factor to consider when discussing communication is intersubjectivity. A good question to ask is: "does my design say the same thing to someone in Nigeria as it does to someone in the United States of America?" A good design will speak everyone's language. Communication is to be closely examined during the design process.

In conclusion, I will like to attempt to debunk a common myth which is that the "Wheel" was the first and greatest invention. My proposition is that, rather than the wheel, the knife or sharp object which were

eventually used to carve the wheel is the greatest human invention or discovery. This goes back to the conclusion of the Optimality of Design section that talks about history. History is to be closely examined and does not necessarily have any effect on the future but tells us how we got to where we are now. Understanding how we got to the present, allows us to accurately imagine the future. However, sometimes we tend to get too caught up in the moment and forget about the history that got us here, ***it's like an idea, you get these great thoughts and ideas and completely forget about the true inspiration behind those thoughts and ideas.***

RESEARCH PROMPTS - ChatGPT

1. I have been working on this over the last couple of minutes since we started the discussion. Our information function will be determined by 2 variables I_q and I_a which are the quality of information and the amount of information respectively. Similarly our concept function will be determined by 2 variables C_u and C_n which are the uniqueness of the concepts and the number of variations of the concepts. The "best or optimal design" will be the integral of the information function over a specific period of time plus the integral of the concept function over a specific period of time. Can you write this out as a formula for me and then let's analyze/prove this.
2. It appears to me that the factors that influence the quality of the information and uniqueness of the concept also depend on other factors. Can we derive the quantum factors?
3. I'd like to build on what we have so far let's start with Quality of Information determined based on three major factors for an type of concept field and concept design: Accuracy of information, relevance of information and persistence of information (i.e. does this particular piece of information stand the test of time)
4. This is quite interesting and a good start. I want us to get a little more granular. Let's use AI as an example. 30 years ago Information relating to an AI concept design say AI powered earphones may not have been as relevant as it is today. So we will need to come up with a scale with which to measure the relevance $R(t)$ at a given time even if we are going to use the scale of 0 to 1, how do we assign the score from 0 to 1?

5. What are some word to describe the opposite of the word Saturation?
6. These are all interesting so how might our formula for creativity be applied to these concepts particularly the artsy one like music, graphic design and fashion. And what would be some good sources of data like the patent library?
7. For market size I'm thinking we can do something similar to what we did for the creativity function. We have a benchmark of the size of the most valuable company/concept in the industry which could then be compared to the size of the immediate market of the company/concept. This is obviously a little abstract but that's where my mind is. Technological feasibility is a bit complex. How might we calculate that from a patent database? The last factor is cost effectiveness not competition. How might we estimate that?
8. How do we come up with a realistic chance of success for each solution? Is it possible to search for information on this?
9. Can you define the abstract meaning of the mathematical operation of multiplication or product?
10. Is this a logical statement in the context of our theory of design: Naturally, the more information there is the lower the value of the accuracy
11. What are the different types of designs ?
12. What is the difference between an idea and a concept?

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